

Dynamic Analysis of Suspension System Used in All-Terrain Vehicle

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ABSTRACT

The suspension of a road vehicle is usually designed with two objectives namely: to isolate the vehicle body from road irregularities and to maintain contact of the wheels with the roadway. Independent suspension systems can be provided by a variety of linkages between the stub axle carrying the wheel and the vehicle chassis. The most popular combinations in modern passenger cars are the double wishbone suspension system. The double wishbone configurations can give vertical movement close to perpendicular relative to the tire-contact surface. The wishbone linkage arrangement provides very good wheel adhesion and optimum wheel control. In addition, the double wishbone suspension system provides a whole new range of possibilities regarding the application of computer systems which would provide active suspension control to suite various conditions.

The main aim of this project is to optimize the upper control arm, lower control arm, and knuckle of the wishbone suspension system to loading. The present project work has created a Finite Element Model for wishbone suspension using Solid work. Later the boundary conditions, material properties and analysis were done in Ansys software.

Keywords: -All-terrain vehicle, double wishbone, suspension geometry, analysis, FEA.

1. INTRODUCTION

An All-Terrain Vehicle (ATV) is defined by the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) as a vehicle that travels on low pressure tires, with a seat that is straddled by the operator, along with handlebars for steering control. In some vehicles steering wheel similar to passenger cars is also used. As the name suggests it is designed to suspension system. negotiate a wider variety of terrain than most other vehicles. Although it is a street-legal vehicle in some countries, it is not legal within most states and provinces of Australia, the United States and Canada and definitely not in India. By the current ANSI definition, it is intended for use by a single operator, although a change to include 2-seaters is under consideration.

The All-Terrain Vehicle (ATV) was initially developed in the 1960's as a farm town vehicle in isolated, mountainous areas. During spring thaws and rainy seasons, steep mountainous roads were often impassable with conventional vehicles. It soon became a recreational vehicle however, providing transportation to areas inaccessible by other motorized transport. Royal Enfield CO built and put on sale a powered Quadra cycle in 1893 that worked in the same way as, and resembles, a modern quad-bike. ATVs were made in the United States a decade before 3- and 4-wheeled vehicles were introduced by Honda and other Japanese companies. During the 1960s, numerous manufacturers offered similar small off-road vehicles that were designed to float and were capable of traversing swamps, ponds and streams, disciplines as motocross, woods racing, desert racing, hill climbing, ice racing, speedway, tourist trophy, flat track, drag racing and others. The early ATV's was mainly used for agricultural purpose only. But now the definition of ATV is changing. Many countries are allowing ATVs as commercial vehicle, though with the regulations on its use and safety. Now days, ATVs are generally used in defence and sports application redefining the ATV. Now the ATVs are also coming with durable roll cages, added safety of seat and shoulder belts and higher ground clearance making it more rugged vehicle. The rear cargo deck is more useful for hauling camping gear, bales of hay, tools and supplies making it suitable for exploring back country, riding sand dunes, hunting, fishing and camping.

The term "ATV" was originally coined to refer to non-straddle ridden, typically six-wheeled, amphibious ATVs, such as the Jiger produced by the Jiger Corporation, the Amphicat produced by Mobility Unlimited Inc, and the Terra Tiger produced by the Allis-Chalmers Manufacturing Company in the mid-1960s and early 1970s.

With the introduction of straddle ridden ATVs, the term AATV was introduced to define the original amphibious ATV category.

ATVs Sport models are built with performance, rather than utility, in mind. To be successful at fast trail riding, an ATV must have light weight, high power, good suspension, and a low centre of gravity. These machines can be modified for such racing terrain.

The first three-wheeled ATV was the Sperry-Rand Tricart. It was designed in 1967 as a graduate project of John Plessinger at the Cranbrook Academy of Arts near Detroit. The Tricart was straddle-ridden with a sit-in rather than sit-on style (similar to the contemporaneous [Big Wheel toy](#)). In 1968 Plessinger sold the Tricart patents and design rights to Sperry-Rand [New Holland](#) who manufactured them commercially. Numerous small American manufacturers of 3-wheelers followed. These small manufacturers were unable to compete when larger motorcycle companies like Honda entered the market in 1969.

Suzuki was a leader in the development of mass production four-wheeled ATVs. It sold the first model, the 1982 Quad Runner LT125, which was a recreational machine for beginners. Adventure Vehicles of Monroe, Louisiana made the first quad ATV in 1980. They called it the Avenger 400. Prior to that, Adventure Vehicles made 3-wheel ATVs and a dump body utility 3-wheeler using Kohler 8 hp engines and Comet drive systems (Comet centrifugal belt-driven clutch, and a Comet forward, neutral, reverse transaxle, with a rigid rear axle or rear differential option.) The Avenger 400 was a rigid suspension vehicle with a fiberglass body and welded tube construction. It was a rudimentary vehicle reminiscent of the Tote Gote of the 1960s. Suzuki sold the first four-wheeled mini-ATV, the LT50, from 1984 to 1987. After the LT50, Suzuki sold the first ATV with a CVT transmission, the LT80, from 1987 to 2006. The suspension system of an “All-Terrain Vehicle” include durability, light in weight, optimum efficiency and cost effective. The vehicle should also be able to handle different road conditions which also in turn signify that the suspension system should be able to tackle all the on-road conditions. Suspension system includes the shock absorbers, coil springs and linkages that connects the vehicle body to its wheel and helps in relative motion between the two. It also keeps the operator isolated from bumps and other road vibrations.

2. Design

We first determine the chassis dimensions from this step, we decide the track width and finally the turning radius. From these steps, we get the total available space to accommodate the suspension arms. Hence, we consider the fixed points (hard points) and set up the theoretical values into LOTUS software. LOTUS suspension software is mainly used for designing the hard points such that the required kinematic behaviour is achieved. Any number of results can be displayed graphically against bump motion, braking motion and steering motion. These results are updated in real time as the suspension hard points are moved. This software uses different templates to identify specific 3D suspension types. The lengths of the both upper and lower control arms are fixed according to the iteration done in the LOTUS software. At first sample length are taken and designed, different graphs of camber, caster over steer, under steer and kingpin inclination are obtained from LOTUS software and according to the results from the graphs the shapes and lengths of the control arm are fixed. The lengths are then modelled in the CAD software and then analysis is performed for forces and torques for verifying if they will sustain the loads.

Step 1 - The design process starts by first taking approximate dimensions of the arms and other components on paper. These dimensions are derived from

- Wheelbase
- Track width
- Approximate roll centre
- Approximate pitch centre

Step 2 - Based on these approximate values, the design is formulated in the LOTUS software and the draft design is analysed using the available graphs of

- Camber
- Castor
- King pin inclination
- Toe

Step 3 - These parameters are tested with respect to

- 1) Bump
- 2) Steer
- 3) Brake

Fig 1: CAD model of upper arm

Fig 2: CAD model of lower arm

3. NUMERICAL SIMULATION

3.1 Boundary Condition:

In analysis we assumed that the face section of knuckle is fixed with tyre. we are going to analysis three different types of materials which are AISI1018, AISI1040 and AISI1080. These materials are stainless steels and to be draw with 1-inch outer diameter using weldments in solid works. We analyzed the forces developed on it and choose the best one material. The bushes are then developed with another tube of bush able accommodate a M10 bolt and nut system to hold it securely in place with the knuckle.

The lower arm has an additional component in form of suspension clamps to connect the lower arm with the suspension damper. This is the only difference between the upper and lower arm. These clamps have a pivotal role to transmit forces from the wheel to the suspension damper.

Three cases for performing analysis are taken. Case 1 is using material AISI1018 with respect to desired parameters which are 1) steering the vehicle to turn the wheels. Vehicle's steering is connected to the knuckle with help of steering rod, when steering turns in any direction so the wishbone's parameters variated. 2) braking the vehicle and checking the parameter affecting on suspension. 3) bumping of vehicle when vehicle gets over any obstacle the parameters of suspension variated. Case 2 is using material AISI1040 with respect to desired parameters which are steer, brake and bump. Case 3 is using material AISI1080 with respect to desired parameters like steer, brake and bump.

Fig 3: Boundary Conditions Applied on Model

Selection of better type of material for wishbone is done if the total deformation rate and equivalent stress are less in all above cases.

3.2 Forces acting on the suspension

Considering the normal road conditions, the forces acting on the suspension are listed below

- Braking force mainly that comes into existence when brakes are actuated.
- Cornering force acting tangentially when a curve is taken by the vehicle.
- Bump force that is the force that acts on the suspension when the wheels undergo rapid motion.

3.3 Calculation of the forces

- Braking force

a. Longitudinal weight transfer

$$= \frac{\text{acceleration} \times \text{C.G. height} \times \text{mass}}{\text{wheel base} \times 2}$$

$$= \frac{1.78 \times 0.300 \times 270}{1.440 \times 2}$$

$$= 49.78 \text{Kg}$$

b. Vertical load due to braking on the wheel

$$= \left(\frac{\text{mass} \times \text{weight distribution}}{2} + \text{longitudinal weight transfer} \right) \times (g)$$

$$= \left(\frac{270 \times 0.55}{2} + 49.78 \right) \times (9.81)$$

$$= 1216.73 \text{N}$$

c. Frictional force = $1216.73 \times 0.6 = 730 \text{N}$

d. Force upright = $\frac{730}{2} = 365 \text{N}$

e. Moment = $365 \times 0.076 = 28 \text{Nm}$

- Cornering force

a. Lateral load transfer

$$= \frac{\text{acceleration} \times \text{CG height} \times \text{m*wt distribution}}{g \times \text{tract width}}$$

$$= \frac{5.84 \times 0.300 \times 270 \times 0.55}{9.81 \times 1.321}$$

$$= 20 \text{kg}$$

b. Vertical load due to cornering on the wheel

$$= \left(\frac{\text{mass} \times \text{weight distribution}}{2} + \text{lateral weight transfer} \right) \times (g)$$

$$= \left(\frac{270 \times 0.55}{2} + 20 \right) \times (9.81)$$

$$= 925 \text{N}$$

c. Frictional Force = $925 \times 0.6 = 555 \text{N}$

d. Moment due to friction = $555 \times 0.09 = 50 \text{Nm}$

e. Force at upper arm = $\frac{50}{0.0762} = 658 \text{N}$

- Bump force = $[\text{centrifugal force} + A + B] \times C$

Where,

A: Vertical force due to braking,

B: Vertical force due to cornering,

C: Distance from roll case to wheel centre

$$\text{Centrifugal force} = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{mass} \times \text{weight distribution}}{2} \right) \times \text{velocity}^2}{\text{Bump radius}} = \frac{\left(\frac{270 \times 0.55}{2} \right) \times 4.16^2}{1}$$

$$= 1291.12 \text{N}$$

Therefore,

$$\text{Bump force} = [1291.12 + 1216 + 925] \times 0.4064 = 1372 \text{N}$$

3.4 Selection of Material:

For manufacturing of suspension, simulation of the suspension is done on Solid works. To make the suspension economical and light weight. The list of different materials is enlisted.

Table 1: Material properties

Properties	AISI1018	AISI1040	AISI1080
Yield Strength	370MPa	415MPa	425MPa
Tensile Strength	440MPa	620MPa	675MPa
Shear Modulus	80GPa	80GPa	80GPa
Young's Modulus	205GPa	210GPa	210GPa
Thermal Conductivity	51.9W/mK	51.9W/mK	51.9W/mK

Analysis: Case 1: AISI1018

Figure 4: represents the analysis of suspension with requisite boundary conditions for AISI1018 and brake, steer and bump are the parameters of load

Case 2: AISI1040

figure 5: shows the analysis of suspension with requisite boundary conditions for AISI1040 and brake, steer and bump are the parameters of load

Case 3: AISI1080

Figure 6: represents the analysis of suspension with requisite boundary conditions for AISI1080 and brake, steer and bump are the parameters of load

4. RESULT

Figure 4 represents the analysis of suspension with requisite boundary conditions for AISI1018 and brake, steer and bump are the parameters of load. The results of total deformation, directional deformation and von-mises criteria of maximum stress are presented in table 2. Similarly, figure 5 shows the analysis of suspension with requisite boundary conditions for AISI1040 and brake, steer and bump are the parameters of load. The results of total deformation, directional deformation and von-mises criteria of maximum stress are presented in table 2. Also, figure 6 represents the analysis of suspension with requisite boundary conditions for AISI1080 and brake, steer and bump are the parameters of load. The results of total deformation, directional deformation and von-mises criteria of maximum stress are presented in table 2. All above-mentioned parameters are taken as experimental setup and analysed to obtain optimized results for concluding the final material to be selected for fabrication of double wishbone suspension. The simulations are done on Solid works software and the simulation results have been shown in fig 4-6.

Table 2: Result comparing table

	Total deformation (mm)	Directional deformation (mm)	Von-mises stress (MPa)
AISI1018			
Brake	78.583	2.79	68.409
Steer	12.704	0.946	13.88
Bump	92.379	91.924	90.44
AISI1040			
Brake	71.439	2.627	56.437
Steer	11.714	0.869	12.774
Bump	87.152	86.813	81.012
AISI1080			
Brake	68.219	2.446	52.191
Steer	10.789	0.796	11.69
Bump	81.778	81.537	78.224

5. CONCLUSION

- 1) After studying different types of All-Terrain Vehicles, it is crucial to design suspension systems that vary in different road conditions.
- 2) Double wishbone suspension is designed in Solid-works software and tested in different parameters with different materials.
- 3) The model was built in finite elements. We get different values with each material by performing analysis in Ansys software.
- 4) It has been found that AISI1080 is the best-suited material for arms and knuckles. The deformation and von-mises stress are less in all parameters i.e, brake, steer and bump comparatively AISI1018 and AISI 1040.

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